

EFFECT OF CORNER CURVATURE ON PRESS FORMING OF METAL-THERMOPLASTIC CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the development of multi-material components combining metals with carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) has attracted growing attention, particularly in the automotive industry. This approach aims to achieve both weight reduction and cost efficiency, which are essential for enhancing vehicle performance and supporting sustainable manufacturing. Among various types of CFRP, thermoplastic CFRP (CFRTP) offers advantages such as short cycle times and recyclability, making it suitable for high-volume production. This study investigates the feasibility of a press forming method for metal/CFRTP laminated sheets as a preliminary step toward continuous forming processes for hybrid structures. Laminates were fabricated by hot pressing plain-woven CF/PA66 with two types of metal sheets: aluminum alloy A5052 and ferritic stainless steel SUS430. Forming was conducted using a V-type press die under controlled thermal conditions. While the specimens were not bent into full L-shaped profiles, the focus was placed on evaluating interfacial integrity and formability under simplified bending conditions. Experimental results revealed that the die corner geometry and temperature uniformity are critical factors for defect-free forming. In particular, appropriately designed die corners helped suppress delamination and fiber–matrix separation at the metal–CFRTP interface. These findings offer valuable guidance for the design of forming tools and process parameters in hybrid metal/CFRTP manufacturing. This work contributes to the advancement of lightweight multi-material forming technologies and supports the future implementation of efficient, high-speed production methods in automotive applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have attracted significant attention as advanced composite materials due to their exceptional combination of light weight and high mechanical strength. These properties make CFRP particularly appealing for automotive applications, where reducing vehicle weight is directly linked to improved fuel efficiency. Consequently, the use of CFRP in structural components such as frames and body panels has been steadily increasing.

However, despite its advantages, the widespread adoption of CFRP remains limited by two major challenges: its relatively high production cost and instability in the supply chain, which restrict its availability for large-scale manufacturing.

To overcome these limitations, recent research has focused on the development of multi-material structures that combine metals with CFRP[1-5]. These hybrid structures aim to exploit the complementary strengths of both materials—metals for their formability and cost-efficiency, and CFRP for its light weight and high strength.

In this context, the present study investigates the feasibility of a press forming technique for metal/CFRTP (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic) laminated sheets. This work serves as a preliminary step toward the development of roll forming processes, which are better suited for high-speed, large-scale production of hybrid materials. Specifically, laminated plates consisting of metal and

plain-woven thermoplastic composite (CF/PA66) were fabricated using a heat press method. A series of forming experiments was conducted to identify and evaluate the optimal processing conditions for achieving high-quality laminates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The test specimens consisted of a 2.0 mm thick CFRTTP core and 0.5 mm thick metal face sheets, using two types of metals: SUS304 stainless steel and A5052 aluminum alloy.

The CFRTTP core was composed of a plain-woven carbon fiber fabric impregnated with a PA66 (polyamide 66) thermoplastic matrix. The material used was Tepex® 201-C200(x)/50% (LANXESS), with a nominal fiber volume fraction of 50%. Each sheet was cut to a width of 30 mm and a length of 60 mm using a fine cutter.

Two types of metal surface conditions were prepared: untreated and roughened using #240 sandpaper. Surface roughening was performed by placing one side of the metal sheet on a flat surface and evenly abrading it with the sandpaper.

To investigate the effect of interfacial bonding, some specimens included a sheet-type hot-melt adhesive (Aron Melt PPET-1200, TOAGOSEI) placed between the CFRTTP and the metal layers, while others were laminated without adhesive. The experiments were conducted under various conditions: with and without adhesive, with and without metal surface treatment, and with or without applied molding pressure.

Figure 1: Dimension and stacking sequence of test specimen

Table 1: Specimen IDs and Corresponding Experimental Conditions

Specimen ID	adhesive	surface treatment	Pressure
S-P-A	Yes	Yes	Yes
S-P	Yes	Yes	No
P-A	Yes	No	Yes
P	Yes	No	No
S-A	No	Yes	Yes
S	No	Yes	No
A	No	No	Yes
N	No	No	No

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows photographs of the test specimens after V-die press forming. Delamination was observed in both SUS/CFRTTP and AL/CFRTTP specimens, particularly in Specimens S-P-A and S-A. However, this delamination was not consistently correlated with the application of pressure during lamination. For example, while no delamination was observed in press-formed specimens A-P and S-P, delamination occurred in S-P-A despite being formed under pressure. These observations suggest that delamination is caused by factors beyond the initial bonding process.

Figure 3 provides a magnified view of the delaminated regions. Notably, significant dents were found in the metal layers near the upper corners, supporting the hypothesis that local stress concentration causes failure. Furthermore, in specimens without delamination, such as S-P and S, clear interlaminar slippage was observed within the CFRTP layer. This slippage is considered to play a key role in accommodating deformation and thereby preventing delamination.

Figure 2: Photographs of test specimens after V-die press forming: specimens exhibiting delamination (e.g., S-P-A, S-A) and specimens without delamination (e.g., S-P, S).

Figure 3: Evidence of delamination mechanisms: left—local denting in the metal layer due to stress concentration at the upper die corners; right—out-of-plane deformation of the CFRTP layer caused by constrained interlaminar slippage.

Figure 4 shows the bending angles of the SUS/CFRTP and A5052/CFRTP specimens after forming. The results revealed significant variations in the corner angles. Notably, specimens without delamination (e.g., Specimens S-P, P, S, and N) exhibited corner angles close to 90°, suggesting that delamination inhibits proper angle formation. This phenomenon is attributed to the sharpness of the upper die corners, which induces localized plastic deformation in the metal layer.

Furthermore, as shown in Figures 4 and 5, most specimens exhibited bending angles less than 90°, indicating a trend opposite to the typical spring-back behavior observed in metal forming. Detailed analysis revealed that this deviation resulted from a mismatch in the bending angles between the upper and lower dies used in the press. This effect was present in all specimens but was particularly pronounced in Specimens S-P-A, P-A, S-A, and A.

From the above findings, delamination was found to occur primarily due to two mechanisms:

- (1) local stress concentration at sharp upper die corners, which induced out-of-plane deformation (denting) in the metal layer, and

- (2) suppression of interlaminar slippage in the CFRTP layer due to non-uniform forming temperature, causing the layers to bend outward and separate from the metal.

These results indicate that appropriate die corner curvature and temperature control are critical for preventing delamination.

Figure 4: Bending angles of SUS/CFRTP and A5052/CFRTP specimens after V-die press forming, showing the influence of delamination on angle formation. Specimens without delamination (e.g., S-P, P, S, N) maintained angles close to 90°, while delaminated specimens exhibited more deviation.

Figure 5: Deviation of actual bending angles from the nominal die angle, highlighting reduced spring-back behavior. The mismatch between upper and lower die angles contributed to angles less than 90° across all specimens.

4 IMPROVEMENT OF A PRESS MOLD

4-1 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

To suppress spring-in deformation during V-bending, an improved mold was employed, in which the corner radius of the upper die was increased and unified with that of the lower die (both set to $R2$). The same materials as in the previous experiments were used, and all specimens included a sheet-type hot-melt adhesive between the CFRTP core and the metal face sheets to ensure consistent interfacial bonding.

Prior to pressing, the specimens were heated in an electric furnace for a total of 8 minutes—4 minutes per side—with flipping at the midpoint to achieve uniform temperature distribution. The V-bending process was then conducted using the improved mold.

Figure 6: Improved die design for V-shaped pressing with unified corner radius ($R2$).

4-2 RESULTS OF PRESS BENDING

As shown in the figure, V-bending was successfully achieved without inducing spring-in deformation. Most specimens exhibited interlaminar slippage, and delamination was effectively suppressed. These findings indicate that the combination of uniform heating and improved die geometry contributed to stable and defect-free forming behavior.

Figure 7: Test specimens after V-shaped pressing using the improved mold.

5 TENSILE PROPERTIES OF METAL/CFRTP LAMINATES

5-1 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD FOR TENSILE TESTING

To evaluate the tensile properties of SUS430/CFRTP and A5052/CFRTP laminated plates, tensile tests were conducted according to standard procedures. Photographs of the test specimens are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Test specimens of SUS430/CFRTP and A5052/CFRTP laminates for tensile testing.

5-2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING USING ABAQUS

Finite element analysis was performed to obtain the corresponding stress–strain curves. The metal layers were modeled as elastoplastic materials, while the CFRTP core was treated as orthotropically elastic. Tensile loading was applied until the metal layers reached their respective yield strains: 1.3% for SUS430/CFRTP and 8% for A5052/CFRTP.

To complement the experimental results, finite element models were developed in Abaqus to simulate the same sandwich configurations under uniaxial tensile loading. Second-order solid elements were employed to accurately represent geometry and deformation behavior.

5-3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 10(a) shows the stress–strain curves for SUS/CFRTP, and Figure 10(b) shows those for AL/CFRTP. In Figure 10(a), the curve for SUS/CFRTP showed yielding at approximately 0.001 strain, followed by a nearly linear increase in stress up to 0.0058 strain. At this strain, the slope changed, indicating the onset of delamination. Beyond a strain of 0.0083, the strain increased sharply, and further measurement became impossible. This indicated that the metal layer and CFRTP had completely delaminated.

On the other hand, in Figure 10(b), the AL/CFRTP curve exhibited a linear increase in stress up to a strain of 0.0032, followed by delamination at that strain, and complete delamination occurred at a strain of 0.0039. Therefore, no clear yield point was observed in this material. This was attributed to the smaller stiffness difference between the aluminum alloy and CFRTP compared to SUS. However, since yielding occurred when the stress in the AL layer reached the yield condition, yielding had already taken place in the AL layer of AL/CFRTP at a strain of 0.003, and residual stress remained after unloading.

For both materials, CFRTP remained elastic even after the complete yielding of the metal layer, so the stress continued to increase. This indicated that defining the 0.2% proof stress was difficult, unlike in the case of a bare metal.

Figure 10: Stress-strain curves of SUS430/CFRTP and A5052/CFRTP

Figure 11: Stress-strain diagram of sus430/CFRTP and A5052/CFRTP(Abaqus)

The results indicate that the overall behavior of both laminates closely resembles the experimental findings. A distinct yield point was observed in the SUS/CFRTP laminate, whereas such a point was not evident in the AL/CFRTP laminate.

The calculated Young's modulus was 94 GPa for SUS/CFRTP and 58 GPa for AL/CFRTP. The former exceeded the experimentally measured value, while the latter was lower. This discrepancy is likely attributed to the presence of an adhesive layer approximately 100 μm thick in the experimental specimens, which was not included in the simulations.

Based on these results, it can be concluded that the stiffness and strength of FMLs using SUS are inferior to those of bare SUS, whereas in the case of AL, both the stiffness and yield stress are only slightly lower than those of the bare metal. However, after yielding, the load is elastically supported by the CFRTP layer, suggesting that the ultimate tensile strength of the laminate may exceed that of the metal alone. These mechanical properties are expected to vary significantly depending on the layup configuration, and thus optimization of the laminated structure is essential for application-specific performance.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the press forming behavior and mechanical performance of metal/CFRTP laminates using V-shaped dies. Key findings are summarized as follows:

- Delamination suppression requires both uniform heating of the CFRTP core and appropriate die corner geometry. Interlaminar slippage plays a crucial role in absorbing deformation without damaging the laminate interface.

- Spring-in behavior was mitigated by matching the upper and lower die radii and ensuring consistent temperature distribution during molding.
- Tensile tests and FEM analysis revealed that CFRTP layers remain elastic after metal yielding, contributing to the post-yield load-bearing capacity. A clear yield point was observed in SUS/CFRTP but not in AL/CFRTP due to differences in stiffness contrast.
- Young's modulus discrepancies between experiment and simulation were mainly attributed to the neglected adhesive layer in FEM. Additionally, thickness variation during molding reduced structural uniformity.

Future improvements should focus on better thickness control and test configurations that load both metal and CFRTP layers more uniformly. Such refinements will enable the design of optimized laminates with enhanced formability and strength for automotive applications.

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